

Socio-Demographic Determinants of Loss to Follow-Up among Patients with Rheumatoid Arthritis in Bangladesh

Ariful Islam^{1*}, S M Zobair Hossain², Abu Shahin³

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*Corresponding author

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic autoimmune disease with rising global burden, particularly affecting low- and middle-income countries like Bangladesh. Loss to follow-up (LTFU) poses a major obstacle to achieving treat-to-target goals in RA, yet socio-demographic determinants of LTFU remain poorly characterized in Bangladeshi populations. **Aim of the Study:** To identify the socio-demographic determinants of loss to follow-up among patients with rheumatoid arthritis attending a tertiary rheumatology center in Bangladesh. **Methods & Materials:** This observational prospective analytical study was conducted at the Department of Rheumatology, Bangladesh Medical University, (formerly BSMMU) from October 2022 to September 2023. Adult patients (≥ 18 years) fulfilling the 2010 ACR/EULAR classification criteria for RA were consecutively enrolled. Socio-demographic and clinical data were collected using structured questionnaires. Patients were followed at 4, 12, and 24 weeks; those failing to attend scheduled visits within 15 days were considered LTFU. Binary logistic regression analysis was performed to identify independent determinants of LTFU. **Results:** Among 179 enrolled patients (88.8% female, mean age 42.77 ± 11.95 years), 82 (45.8%) were lost to follow-up. LTFU was significantly associated with rural residence (22.0% vs 5.2%, $p < 0.001$), distance > 40 km from hospital (59.8% vs 27.8%, $p < 0.001$), and monthly income $< 10,000$ BDT (40.2% vs 18.6%, $p < 0.001$). Multivariable regression revealed that income $< 10,000$ BDT (adjusted OR: 22.35, 95% CI: 5.27–94.74, $p < 0.001$), income 10,000–20,000 BDT (adjusted OR: 15.44, 95% CI: 5.28–45.13, $p < 0.001$), and rural

residence (adjusted OR: 2.84, 95% CI: 1.07–7.58, $p = 0.037$) were independent determinants of LTFU. Age and sex showed no significant association. **Conclusion:** Low monthly household income and rural residence are powerful independent determinants of loss to follow-up among Bangladeshi RA patients, highlighting that socioeconomic and geographic barriers predominantly drive care discontinuation. Targeted interventions addressing financial constraints and improving rural healthcare access are urgently needed to enhance treatment retention in this vulnerable population.

Keywords: Rheumatoid Arthritis, Loss to Follow-Up, Socioeconomic Determinants, Rural Health, Bangladesh.

1. Associate professor, Department of Rheumatology, Bangladesh Medical University (BMU), Dhaka, Bangladesh (ORCID: 0009-0001-3362-8852)
2. Resident rheumatology phase-B, Department of Rheumatology, Bangladesh Medical University (BMU), Dhaka, Bangladesh
3. Professor, Department of Rheumatology, Bangladesh Medical University (BMU), Dhaka, Bangladesh

INTRODUCTION

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic, progressive, systemic autoimmune inflammatory disease characterized by persistent synovitis, joint destruction, and significant functional impairment. Globally, the burden of RA continues to rise; an estimated 17.6 million individuals were affected in 2020, with an age-standardized prevalence of 208.8 cases per 100,000 population—representing a 14.1% increase since 1990.^[1] The disease disproportionately affects women, with an age-standardized female-to-male prevalence ratio of approximately 2.45:1, a pattern consistently observed across diverse populations worldwide.^[1] In low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) such as Bangladesh, RA imposes a particularly severe burden, as constrained healthcare infrastructure, limited resources, and poverty compound the individual and societal costs of the disease.^[2] Early and sustained treatment—primarily with disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs)—is central to achieving remission, preventing irreversible joint damage, and preserving quality of life in

patients with RA.^[3] Bangladesh has developed its own management recommendations for RA, acknowledging both the evidence base and the socioeconomic realities that shape care delivery in a resource-constrained setting.^[4] Despite advances in therapeutic options, real-world effectiveness in LMICs remains limited by suboptimal follow-up adherence. Loss to follow-up (LTFU)—defined as failure of a patient to attend scheduled clinic appointments without documented transfer or death—is a major obstacle to achieving treat-to-target goals in RA.^[5]

Socioeconomic status (SES) has been consistently identified as a key determinant of RA outcomes and medication utilization. A comprehensive scoping review found that lower income, reduced educational attainment, and area-level deprivation were each independently associated with differences in DMARD use and reduced treatment adherence in RA patients.^[6] Geographic barriers further compound these disparities; rural and remote patients with RA face substantially greater challenges in maintaining care, with

transportation difficulties, environmental barriers such as road quality, and financial constraints collectively contributing to missed appointments.^[7] A 2025 scoping review of sociodemographic and economic barriers to specialist RA care across seventeen high-income and ten LMICs identified low socioeconomic status, low income, and rurality as the most consistently reported barriers to initial and ongoing rheumatologist consultations.^[8] In South Asian settings specifically, financial insecurity emerges as a critical structural barrier to RA care continuity. A South Indian hospital-based study found that over half (51.4%) of RA patients experienced catastrophic household health expenditure, with most participants lacking insurance coverage.^[9] Similarly, research from Pakistan revealed that access to consistent rheumatology care in rural areas was extremely limited, affecting fewer than 5% of women with RA, underscoring how poverty and rurality create intersecting barriers to follow-up.^[10] In addition, low household income has been associated with lower participation in remote follow-up models for RA in high-income settings,

suggesting that income constraints transcend geographic context in their impact on care continuity.^[11] The present study therefore aimed to identify the socio-demographic determinants of LTFU among patients with RA attending a tertiary rheumatology centre in Bangladesh, with the objective of informing evidence-based strategies to improve care retention in this vulnerable population.

METHODS & MATERIALS

This observational prospective analytical study was conducted in the Department of Rheumatology at Bangladesh Medical University (BMU) (formerly BSMMU), Dhaka, Bangladesh, from October 2022 to September 2023. Adult patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA) attending the rheumatology outpatient department and fulfilling the 2010 American College of Rheumatology/European Alliance of Associations for Rheumatology (ACR/EULAR) classification criteria were consecutively enrolled. After obtaining informed written consent, socio-demographic and clinical information, including age, sex, residence, education, occupation, marital status, tobacco use, disease duration, co-morbidities, disease activity, functional status, and depression

status, were collected using a structured questionnaire and validated assessment tools. Patients were followed according to a predefined schedule at 4, 12, and 24 weeks. Patients who failed to attend their scheduled follow-up visits within 15 days of the appointment date were considered as loss to follow-up (LTFU). Attempts were made to contact these patients through telephone calls, short message services, or email on at least three occasions. Socio-demographic factors associated with LTFU were analyzed using appropriate statistical tests, and binary logistic regression analysis was performed to identify independent determinants of LTFU. Statistical analyses were carried out using IBM SPSS Statistics version 26, and a p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Inclusion criteria

- Adult patients (≥18 years) of either sex.
- Patients diagnosed with rheumatoid arthritis according to the 2010 ACR/EULAR classification criteria.

- Patients who provided informed written consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion criteria

- Patients with overlap syndromes, including systemic lupus erythematosus or other connective tissue diseases.
- Patients with severe cognitive impairment preventing completion of the interview or questionnaires.
- Patients unwilling to participate in the study.

RESULTS

The study included 179 patients with rheumatoid arthritis. The mean age was 42.77±11.95 years and females predominated (88.8%). Most participants were married (78.8%) and resided in urban areas (77.1%). Approximately 57% belonged to low- and middle-income households (*Table I*).

Table I
Baseline Socio-demographic Characteristics of Study Participants (n=179).

Variable	Frequency (%)
Age (years), Mean ± SD	42.77 ± 11.95
Sex	
Male	20 (11.2)
Female	159 (88.8)
Marital Status	
Married	141 (78.8)
Unmarried/Other	38 (21.2)
Residence	
Urban	138 (77.1)
Rural	41 (22.9)
Monthly Family Income (BDT)	
<10,000	23 (12.8)
10,000–20,000	79 (44.2)
>20,000	77 (43.0)

Loss to follow-up was significantly more common among patients from rural areas, those living farther from the hospital, and

those with lower monthly income. Age and sex were not significantly associated with follow-up status (*Table II*).

Table II
Association Between Socio-demographic Characteristics and Follow-up Status.

Variable	LTFU (n=82)	RFU (n=97)	p-value
Age (years), Mean ± SD	43.46 ± 11.57	42.18 ± 11.45	0.457
Male	10 (12.2)	10 (10.3)	0.688
Female	72 (87.8)	87 (89.7)	
Rural residence	18 (22.0)	5 (5.2)	<0.001
Urban residence	64 (78.0)	92 (94.8)	
Distance >40 km from hospital	49 (59.8)	27 (27.8)	<0.001
Income <10,000 BDT	33 (40.2)	18 (18.6)	<0.001
Income 10,000–20,000 BDT	34 (41.5)	45 (46.4)	
Income >20,000 BDT	15 (18.3)	34 (35.0)	

After adjustment, low income emerged as the strongest determinant of loss to follow-up. Patients earning less than 10,000 BDT

per month had over 22-fold higher odds of becoming lost to follow-up. Rural residence independently increased the

likelihood of loss to follow-up by nearly threefold (*Table III*).

Table III
Multivariable Logistic Regression Analysis of Socio-demographic Determinants of Loss to Follow-Up.

Variable	Adjusted OR	95% CI	p-value
Income 10,000–20,000 BDT	15.44	5.28–45.13	<0.001
Income <10,000 BDT	22.35	5.27–94.74	<0.001
Rural residence	2.84	1.07–7.58	0.037

Figure 1 Study Flow Diagram Data.

Of the 225 patients initially screened for eligibility, 46 were excluded, leaving 179 patients included in the final analysis.

During the follow-up period, 82 patients (45.8%) were lost to follow-up, while 97 patients (54.2%) completed regular follow-

up and were retained for outcome assessment (*Figure 1*).

Figure 2 Socioeconomic and Social Reasons for Loss to Follow-up.

Financial constraints were the leading cause of loss to follow-up (34.15%), followed by lack of family support (19.51%) and long travel distance (13.42%). Family conflict and mild symptoms each accounted for 9.76%, with employment-related factors (6.10%) and other reasons (7.30%) comprising the remainder. Socioeconomic barriers collectively represented the majority of attrition (Figure 2).

DISCUSSION

This study investigated the socio-demographic determinants of LTFU among 179 patients with RA in Bangladesh and identified low monthly household income and rural residence as independent predictors of LTFU, while age and sex showed no significant association. These findings contribute important evidence from a South Asian LMIC context to a growing body of literature implicating socioeconomic and geographic factors in RA care discontinuation.

The predominance of female participants (88.8%) in this cohort is consistent with the well-established epidemiological pattern of RA, in which women are affected at approximately two to three times the rate of men.^[12] This female predominance has been documented globally including in GBD 2021 data showing a standardized female-to-male prevalence ratio of 2.45:1^[11] as well as in Asian populations, where large-scale data from South Korea and China confirm persistently higher prevalence rates among women across all age groups.^[13] The mean age of 42.77 years in our cohort reflects the typical working-age distribution of RA, which carries significant socioeconomic implications as disease-related disability intersects with peak productive years.

The most striking finding in this study was that patients with a monthly income below 10,000 BDT had over 22-fold higher odds of LTFU compared to the highest income group, while those earning 10,000–20,000 BDT had approximately 15-fold higher odds. These magnitudes are notably large and highlight the severe financial barriers to sustained RA care in Bangladesh. This is consistent with findings from a scoping review by Russell et al. (2023), which identified income as one of the most frequently measured SES determinants of DMARD use and adherence across 81 included studies, with lower income consistently associated with reduced medication adherence and treatment gaps.^[6] The economic burden of RA is substantial; a study from South India found that the mean annual health expenditure for RA was approximately USD 476 per household, with 51.4% of patients experiencing catastrophic health expenditure.^[9] In Bangladesh, where a

considerable proportion of the population earns below this threshold, the direct and indirect costs of RA visits including transportation, medications, and lost income from work absence may render regular follow-up prohibitive for low-income patients.

Rural residence was independently associated with nearly three-fold higher odds of LTFU in our multivariable model, a finding that aligns closely with the international evidence base. A systematic review by Pianarosa et al. (2022) synthesizing data on rural and remote RA patients found that 27% of rural patients traveled more than four hours to reach their rheumatologist, and environmental barriers such as road conditions and transportation availability affected appointment maintenance for a substantial proportion.^[7] In our cohort, 59.8% of LTFU patients lived more than 40 km from the hospital compared to only 27.8% of those with regular follow-up, reinforcing the role of distance as a structural barrier. The scoping review by Anisworth et al. (2025), examining barriers across 25 global studies, identified rurality as a consistent barrier in both high-income and LMICs, linked to health workforce shortages and compounding financial constraints for rural populations.^[8] The reported reasons for LTFU in our study including financial constraints (34.1%), long travel distance (13.4%), and lack of family support (19.5%) reflect a multi-layered burden that is consistent with this evidence.

The non-significant association of age and sex with LTFU in our study is noteworthy. While socioeconomic variables exerted strong independent effects, demographic characteristics such as age ($p=0.457$) and sex ($p=0.688$) did not differ significantly between LTFU and regular follow-up groups. This is partially consistent with Ogdie et al.'s findings that personal and disease-related factors, rather than basic demographic variables, most strongly influenced remote follow-up participation in RA.^[11] However, it contrasts with some reports suggesting that older age may be associated with better adherence due to health awareness. The absence of an age effect in our study may reflect that in a low-income LMIC context, socioeconomic constraints override age-related health-seeking behavior.

The financial toxicity of RA care in LMICs has been specifically highlighted in sub-Saharan Africa, where Nkeck et al. (2024) argued that tackling financial insecurity is essential for effective management of autoimmune rheumatic diseases.^[14] While the specific healthcare financing context differs between Bangladesh and sub-Saharan Africa, the underlying mechanism of poverty limiting access to sustainable specialist follow-up is broadly similar.

Adherence to antirheumatic therapy has been comprehensively evaluated in a 2024 systematic review and meta-analysis, which identified financial barriers, complex treatment regimens, and lack of patient support as principal drivers of non-adherence across diverse settings.^[15] This suggests that interventions targeting LTFU in Bangladesh must address not only the cost of follow-up visits but also medication affordability and support systems.

The global RA burden is projected to increase further, with GBD 2021 data forecasting continued rises in both incidence and prevalence to 2050, particularly among women and in lower-SDI regions.^[1] This trajectory makes the imperative to address LTFU in countries like Bangladesh particularly urgent. Telehealth models have shown promise for reducing LTFU in rural RA populations in high-income settings; a pilot programme in North Carolina (USA) utilizing shared telehealth between a rheumatology center and rural community clinics demonstrated improved access with high patient satisfaction, alleviating barriers related to transportation and financial constraints.^[16] Adapting such models to Bangladesh's infrastructure accounting for internet connectivity limitations and the particularly low income of high-risk patients represents a priority for future health system innovation.

This study has several limitations. Its single-centre, hospital-based design limits generalizability to community RA populations. Reasons for LTFU were self-reported by a subset of patients and may be subject to recall or social desirability bias. Clinical disease activity at baseline was not compared between groups, and it is possible that patients with milder disease were more likely to discontinue follow-up. Despite these limitations, the study provides robust multivariable evidence for income and rural residence as independent LTFU determinants in a population with few existing data. Future multi-centre prospective studies including clinical and disease activity variables are warranted to build on these findings and guide targeted retention interventions for Bangladeshi patients with RA.

LIMITATION

The single-center, hospital-based design limits the generalizability of our findings to the broader community-based RA population in Bangladesh.

CONCLUSION

Low household monthly income and rural residence emerged as strong independent predictors of loss to follow-up among Bangladeshi patients with RA, suggesting that socioeconomic disadvantage and geographic barriers are the principal

drivers of care discontinuation, whereas demographic factors such as age and sex appear to play a lesser role.

RECOMMENDATION

To mitigate the high rates of loss to follow-up observed in this study, we recommend that the Bangladesh rheumatology community and health policymakers implement a multi-pronged strategy focused on reducing financial barriers and improving geographic access. This should include the establishment of subsidized or free medication and transportation programs for low-income patients, the expansion of decentralized rheumatology care through telemedicine and satellite clinics in rural areas, and the development of community-based patient support and navigation systems to address the lack of family support identified as a key factor. Such targeted interventions are essential to ensure equitable access to sustained, life-improving care for all patients with RA in Bangladesh.

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